

Teachers' Capacity Building: A Genuine Mechanism for Achieving Human Capital Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined teachers' capacity building as genuine mechanism for achieving human capital development in Nigeria. The study is delimited to Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study. This study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of this study covers all school teachers in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state. The sample of this study consisted of 330 teachers. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 3 out of 9 local government areas that constituted Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state. Twenty schools were selected using the simple random sampling technique of which about 15 teachers were purposively taken from each school. The instrument adopted in the study was the questionnaire titled: Teacher Capacity building Inventory (TCBI). It was constructed by the researcher. The data collected were collated, coded and analyzed with descriptive statistics because of their appropriateness to the research questions. The outcome of the study revealed that the extent to which teachers' capacity building can enhance the achievement of human capital development in Nigeria is very high. There were several challenges militating against teachers' capacity building in Nigeria and that the itemized strategies were laudable for improving teachers' capacity building in Nigeria. Conclusion was reached based on the findings and useful recommendations were made, which include among others that attention should be paid to development programmes that would make teaching career appealing and geared towards achieving human capital development in Nigeria. Government should device more strategies that will enhance capacity building of teachers' Educational administrators and policy formulators should implement policies that would surmount the challenges facing teachers' professional development in Nigeria.

Key Words: Capacity building, human capital development economic growth, industrial development

Introduction

Education is extremely important not only for the success of an individual but for the nation as well. Education is a process of developing knowledge, skills and character of the students. Its major objective is to make an individual learn how to level with the society by developing intellect, equipping one's self to deal with the reality of life and by facilitating realization of self-potential and latent talents of an individual. Education encompasses teaching and learning specific skills, positive judgment, well developed wisdom and profoundness. A successful teacher is required to be equipped with the characteristics like mastery of subject matter, current professional skills, sound physical and mental health, devotion and dedication to his profession to be able to impact on learners and the society.

Teachers have one of the most demanding vocations in the world and in order to fulfill their important roles with excellence, they need training, motivation as well as regular mental, emotional and spiritual rejuvenation. Educational systems all over the world recognize the importance of the teacher. Building an effective model and mechanism that would develop and enhance the teachers' capacity and provide them avenues for professional development should therefore be a priority.

Teachers are the bedrock for all human learning, and they are the hub around which individual citizens are made to realize their full potential to serve their nations (Adu, 2005). The changing classroom practice with technologically changing learning environment requires teachers to keep abreast with these global experiences and improve students' learning achievement. Teaching changes with changing trends and; teachers need to improve their teaching competences, skills and knowledge of teaching practice by undertaking capacity building and taking advantage of available professional development opportunities. Equipping teachers with necessary teaching competencies will contribute to effective implementation of education reforms.

Teachers play a vital role in the society and they are indispensable ingredient in national development. Obanya (2010) posited that teachers remain essential actors and catalyst for change in all efforts aimed at promoting quality education in schools. As agents of change, teachers can promote quality education and improved students' performance in secondary schools. The success of any educational programme depends on the quality and competence of teachers who are the epicenter of the teaching and learning process. No educational system can grow above the level of the teachers in the system. The number of trained teachers is insufficient and devoid of necessary skills and is not regularly exposed to professional development and training programme (UNESCO, 2005). Obanya (2010) argues that teachers require opportunities for continuous self-improvement; both career-long and career-wide opportunities that will enable them to acquire skills, knowledge and techniques needed for quality on the job performance. Darling-Hammond (2012) noted that realization of student achievement gains requires teachers to have; strong content knowledge; pedagogical knowledge and skills of how to teach others; understanding learners and their development; having general abilities for organizing, observing, explaining ideas, thinking diagnostically and having adaptive expertise for making judgment in light of student needs in a given context.

However, despite the well-stated education goals, schools continue to post poor students' results. Empirical evidence and synthesis of literature shows that there are a number of factors contributing to poor performance by students both in internal and external examinations. Yara

and Otieno (2010) explained that the causes of poor students' performance, especially in mathematics are due to poor planning by teachers, inadequate teaching and learning resources and teacher shortages. In addition, poor students' performance has been blamed on teacher preparation. It is imperative for educational stakeholders to build teacher capacity, by organizing seminars, workshops and conferences and to organize mentorship and coaching programs for teachers for overall development of their capacity (Amede, 2016). However, according to IR Global Rankings News Bulletin (2013), seminars and workshops allows participants to explore new ways of doing things, create value, adopt best practices, trends, technology and build networks. This is considered handy in efforts aimed at improving teaching skills and students' performance. However, teacher's capacity building through workshops is considered to be of short term nature, low intensity and unfocused activity (Cole, 2012).

For more than 59 years of independence, Nigeria is yet to achieve meaningful development. Our educational system has not witness significant growth in terms of its contributions towards economic, social, political and educational development. The curriculum remains at variant with the societal needs, obsolete teaching method, poor teaching materials and the teachers, who are at the epicenter of our educational system are clustered with unqualified personnel. The country remains an exporter of raw materials and commodities. Over 90 percent of export earnings and 70 percent of government revenues are derived from crude oil export. Prioritizing capacity building for teachers' education can help to correct the anomalies bedeviling the current curriculum and transform the national economy. Efanya (2015) averred that the future of Nigerian greatness lies in the effectiveness of our schools and the quality of our education. But what is quality education without competent teachers? It is an illusion to think that meaningful developmental stride can be achieved without access to competent teachers.

Human capital development has been identified as tool to promote economic growth and stimulus for industrial development. Its significance and relevance through acquisition of necessary skills is also a prerequisite for socio economic transformation (Amede, 2018). According to him, the wealth and prosperity of a nation rest upon the development of people and the effective contribution to national development, stating that human resources constitutes the ultimate basis for the wealth of nations. According to him, any country, which is unable to develop the skills and knowledge of her people and utilize them effectively in the national economy, would definitely encounter the challenge of sustaining economic growth and industrial development. Quality skills training for teachers tend to increase productivity and competitiveness in a knowledge-based economy by imparting requisite knowledge on students. This would help direct how employments, skills and economic development policy areas could generally be integrated to maximize benefits for the economy and society, as well as to foster business development, and the enhancement of skills and social inclusion.

Quality teachers use ICT base learning interventions to produce high quality graduates. There is an emerging paradigm in the world today to shift towards science and technology. Science courses should be encouraged in schools and harmonizes the policy of education with that of other sectors of the economy (Jegade, 2015). Clearly and incontrovertibly, mathematics, science and technology hold the key to the present and future development in Nigeria, and occupy the role as the major driver towards economy recovery.

Quality teachers encourage the acquisition of creative skills and capacity building for products of our schools system. Adams (2016) stressed that Nigeria needs technical manpower

with sound innovation, creativity and the ability to take risk to help the nation move forward. It is disheartening to note that the crude oil that sustains our economy is under the control of foreign expatriates. It is expected that our educational system should develop skillful personnel in engineering, agriculture, health, technocrats, administrators etc. to mention just a few.

Quality teachers can train our youths to become agro entrepreneurs and can use Agriculture to tackle her unemployment problems and economy recovery. Nigeria has 910,768 km² of arable land, 13,000 km² of water and over 21 agricultural research institutes. We have good weather condition with abundant rainfall and sunshine all the year round. We have large and healthy population of which about 60 percent is made up of youths under 35 years of age. The land is fertile and has different ecological zones to grow different types of plants. Quality education teaches youth's modern skills of farming. Youths are taught how to use herbicides, insecticides, pesticides, fertilizers and current farming innovation in both animal and crop production. Well-trained teachers will help to engage the teeming unemployed youths and improve the much talked about internally generated revenue.

Ogbonna (2016) noted that the solution to graduate unemployment is not atomic science but a matter of mindset and orientation to encourage young entrepreneurs. Youth entrepreneurs are reliable engine for economic growth, generation of new wealth, encourages exportation and hit the glass ceiling in terms of income. Entrepreneurs bring about discoveries, innovations and creativity in the country, thereby engineering multiplier effect into the economy. Entrepreneurs contribute to the economy through job creation, use of technologies, production of goods and services, creation of new market, added wealth and raise the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the nation and earning of foreign exchange.

Competent teachers can develop technical skills on youths and encourage self-employment. Nigeria is one of the top three countries in the world that have the largest population of poor people, with more than half the population living in less than one dollar a day. National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2014) asserted that a staggering 112.519 million Nigerians live in relatively poor conditions. The figure represents 69% of the country's total population estimated to be 180 million. According to Osinbanjo (2016), 110 million Nigerians, implying 6 out of 10 Nigerians live in abject poverty. The sociological consequences are social deprivation, insecurity, criminality, kidnapping, street urchins and beggars which abound across the country. Quality education has the potentials to revamp the economy and create job opportunities that will eventually reduce poverty in Nigeria. This can be achieved through the empowerment of youths by availing them access to quality education, useful skill acquisition, creating enabling environment for developing their potentials and equipping teachers with pedagogical knowledge.

The results of the research findings in many studies have shown that the role of the teacher in determining students' performance is significant (OECD, 2009). Equipping teachers with necessary teaching competencies will contribute to effective implementation of education reforms. In order to develop a responsive and effective teacher capable of undertaking the foregoing, Obanya (2010) argues that teachers require opportunities for continuous self-improvement; both career-long and career-wide opportunities that will enable them to acquire skills, knowledge and techniques needed for quality on the job performance. Sanyal (2013) noted that an effective teacher can only be developed by quality professional preparation resulting from quality career long professional development.

The poor quality of teachers' education in Nigeria has multiplying effects on the social, economic, moral and political indices. Nigerian educational system prioritizes paper qualification at the expense of vocational skills. That is why, for instance, most engineers cannot perform simple engineering feats, university graduates are dependent on white collar jobs, agricultural graduates lack farming methodologies and techniques, etc. This is because Nigerian educational system, according to Gamalier (2018), is an expired one. Only competent teachers can reverse the trend. The focus of this study is to determine teachers' capacity building as genuine mechanism achieving human capital development in Nigeria.

Statement of Problems

The changing classroom practice with technologically changing learning environment requires teachers to keep abreast with these global experiences and improve students' learning achievement. Teaching changes with changing trends and; teachers need to improve their teaching competences, skills and knowledge of teaching practice by undertaking capacity development and taking advantage of available professional development opportunities. Neglects of this vital necessity have hunted the quest for achieving human capital development in Nigeria. Industrial development has been on its lowest ebb; the national economic indicators of GDP, inflation, unemployment, foreign debts, export etc. are at their worst possible rates. Inflation shrank at 17.85%, GDP contracted by 2.06% and the economy by 0.36%. Exchange rates with other major currencies have depreciated more than 40%, per capita income has been all time low and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria shrank. The needs for training in education, particularly for teachers are vital to improve the quality of education. Teachers are crucial in implementing educational reforms in accordance with the aspiration of the National Philosophy of Education. The success of a school curriculum is closely related to its effective implementation. Teachers have to be personally aware of the school curriculum, improve and enhance the necessary skills to interpret the concepts accurately and to implement the modified curriculum according its requirements, aims and objectives. These underscore the need capacity building for Nigerian teachers.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine determine teachers' capacity building as genuine mechanism achieving human capital development in Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Examine the extent to which teachers' capacity building can enhance the achieving human capital development in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state.
2. Investigate the strategies for improving teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state.
3. Determine the major challenges militating against teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state.

Research Questions

1. To what extent can teachers' capacity building enhance the achievement of human capital development in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state?
2. What are the major challenges militating against teachers' capacity building in Nigeria?
3. What are the strategies for improving teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state?

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted in this study. A descriptive survey involves asking the same set of questions that are often prepared in the form of written questionnaire or ability test to a large number of individuals either by mail, by telephone or in person. The population of this study covers all school teachers in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 3 out of 9 local government areas that constituted Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state. Twenty five schools were selected using the simple random sampling technique of which about 14 teachers were purposively taken from each school. A sample of 330 teachers constituted the study.

The major research instrument adopted in the study was the questionnaire titled: Teachers Capacity Building Inventory (TCBI). It was constructed by the researcher. The questionnaire was divided into four sections, Section A seeks to find out the bio-data of the respondents, B teachers' Capacity Building and human capital development in Nigeria), Section C addresses strategies for improving teachers' capacity building while Section D has issues relating to challenges militating against teachers' capacity building. Sections B - D have ten items each to which the respondents were expected to provide answers. The liker type scale of strongly agreed [SA] 4 points, agreed [A] 3points, strongly disagreed [AD] 2 points and disagreed [D] 1point was used to rate the reaction of the respondents to the items contained in the questionnaires.

Validation of the Instrument

A sample of the instrument was shown to some research experts for corrections and their comments were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument to ensure that it had content validity. The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering it on a sample of 30 teachers in Apapa local government area of Lagos state, which was not part of the original sample population. The data from the tests were analyzed with Cronbach alpha. The coefficient of reliability average was estimated to 0.81, indicating that there was consistency and reliability in the questionnaire items.

Method of Data Collection

A total number of three hundred and nine (339) questionnaires were administered to teachers in the twenty selected schools. The questionnaires were administered by the researchers and two research assistants to ensure that copies of the questionnaire got to the respondents at the right time and subsequently retrieved. In each of the twenty selected schools, teachers who were capable, available, and could give the needed responses promptly were purposively selected by the researchers and were given a set of questionnaire each to respond to. Some of the respondents completed and submitted their questionnaires the same day while others asked the

researchers to come for it later. 330 copies of the questionnaires administered to the respondents were correctly filled and retrieved, which constituted 97% success.

The data collected were collated, coded and analyzed using basic frequency and descriptive statistics because of their appropriateness to the study. The data was processed and analyzed with Microsoft excels and the SPSS statistical analysis software. Weighted mean was used to answer the research questions. A mean below 2.5 was considered to be low while above 2.5 was taken as high.

Results

This section presents the findings of the study. The results of the statistical analysis with reference to the research questions are presented.

A total of 339 teachers were administered with questionnaires. 330 of the questionnaires were returned and duly completed. The response of questionnaires analyzed were 330 which was equivalent to 97 %.

Table 1 Distribution of Questionnaires and response rate

Details	Number
Total of given questionnaires	339
Returned questionnaires	330
Omitted questionnaires	9
Analyzed questionnaires	330

Source: Field Data, 2019.

Characteristics of respondents

The researcher collected personal information from the respondents to enable her to define the demographic characteristics of the teachers and for that matter, they were tabulated in categories.

Gender distribution

The gender of respondents was tabulated and presented in table 4.2.

Table 2: Gender of respondents according to the survey

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	149	45.2	45.2	45.2
Female	181	54.8	54.8	100.0
Total	330	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Data, 2019.

The study revealed that 149 of the respondents were male while 181 were female. This indicated the participants to be 45.2% and 54.8% for males and females respectively. Females therefore constituted a higher percentage of the sample. However this did not have any impact on the findings.

Teachers Experience Status Distribution

Table 3: Teachers Experience of respondents

Experience	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Below 9years	76	23.0	23.0	23.0
10-15	91	27.6	27.6	50.6
16years and Above	163	49.4	49.4	100.0
Total	330	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Data, 2019.

Teachers' experience of respondents was tabulated and presented in table 3. The study revealed that 76 (23.0%) of the respondents were below 9 years of experience, 91 were between 10-15 years while 163 (49.4%) were 16 years and above (49.4%).

Table 4: Teachers' Position According to the Survey

Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Principals	31	9.4	9.4	9.4
Teachers	299	90.6	90.6	100.0
Total	330	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Data, 2019.

This percentage of the categories of Teachers' Position are 31 (9.4%) are Principals while 299 (90.6%) are school teachers. Majority of respondents were school teachers

Table 5: Academic Qualifications of Teachers

Qualifications	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid NCE	88	26.7	26.7	26.7
Degree	145	43.9	43.9	70.6
Post Graduate	97	29.4	29.4	100.0
Total	330	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Data, 2019.

Academic Qualifications of Teachers was tabulated and presented in table 5. The study revealed that 88 (26.7%) of the respondents were NCE holders, 145(43.9%) has degree while 97 (29.4%) were Post Graduate holders.

Research question 1: To what extent can teachers’ capacity building enhance the achievement of human capital development in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state?

Table 5: Mean rating on the extent to which teachers’ capacity building would enhance the achievement of human capital development in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state

S/N	Statements	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q1	Teachers’ capacity building helps teachers to facilitates the training of students with industrial skills	330	972.00	2.95	.95	Agreed
Q2	Teachers’ capacity building helps teachers to inculcate entrepreneurship mindset on students	330	1125.00	3.41	.71	Agreed
Q3	Teachers’ capacity building enables teachers to produce students with high technological skills for industries.	330	1101.00	3.34	.71	Agreed
Q4	Teachers’ capacity building inculcate ICT Skill for teachers to enhance learners scientific innovation	330	949.00	2.88	1.01	Agreed

Q5	Teachers' capacity building enables teachers to imbibe technical education on learners	330	1058.00	3.21	.78	Agreed
Q6	Teachers' capacity building helps to produce competent teachers that will advocate vocational education	330	1074.00	3.25	.85	Agreed
Q7	Teachers' capacity building enables teachers to produce students with practical skills that will encourage industrial establishment	330	1147.00	3.48	.70	Agreed
Q8	Teachers' capacity building enables teachers to encourage human capital development needed in industries.	330	1070.00	3.24	.75	Agreed
Q9	Teachers' capacity building enables teachers to develop knowledge economy on students	330	1077.00	3.26	.78	Agreed
Q10	Teachers' capacity building enables teachers to encourage skill acquisition for self-determination.	330	1086.00	3.29	.77	Agreed
Total		3300	10659	3.23	.80	Agreed

Table 6 above revealed the extent to which teachers' capacity building can enhance the achievement of human capital development in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state. Teachers' capacity building enables teachers to produce students with practical skills that will encourage industrial establishment tops the list with average mean score of 3.48, Teachers' capacity building helps teachers to inculcate entrepreneurship mindset on students (3.41); again by Teachers' capacity building enables teachers to encourage skill acquisition for self-determination (3.29). Next was Teachers' capacity building enables teacher to develop knowledge economy on students (3.26) and lastly by Teachers' capacity building enables teachers to maintain quality education that will facilitate industrial revolution with average mean score of 2.88. The total sum was 10659 and the average means was 3.23. It should be noted that the average sum of all the items on the questionnaire fall above the average bench mark of 2.5. The implication is that the extent to which teachers' capacity building can enhance the achievement of human capital development in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state was very high.

Research question 2: What are the major challenges militating against teachers’ capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state?

Table 7: Descriptive statistics on or challenges militating against teachers’ capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state

S/N	Statements	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev	Remarks
Q1	Inadequate funding of teachers’ capacity building programmes.	330	1001.00	3.03	.89	Agreed
Q2	Negative perception of teachers’ capacity building programmes by government.	330	1025.00	3.11	.79	Agreed
Q3	Poor teachers attitude towards teachers’ capacity building programmes	330	1022.00	3.01	.88	Agreed
Q4	Low teachers awareness towards teachers’ capacity building training	330	972.00	2.95	.95	Agreed
Q5	Inadequate government support for teachers’ capacity building	330	1125.00	3.41	.71	Agreed
Q6	Irregularity of capacity building programmes for teachers	330	1101.00	3.34	.71	Agreed
Q7	Stringent policies towards teachers’ capacity building programmes	330	949.00	2.88	1.01	Agreed
Q8	Inadequate incentive for teachers’ to participate in capacity building programmes	330	1058.00	3.21	.78	Agreed
Q9	Negative perception of teachers’ capacity building programmes by teachers.	330	1074.00	3.25	.85	Agreed
Q10	Inadequate facilitators’ (Resource persons) capacity building training in Nigeria.	330	1147.00	3.48	.70	Agreed
	Total	3300	20948	3.48	.91	Agreed

Table 7 above revealed the descriptive statistics on the major challenges militating against teachers’ capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state. The total score is 20948, average mean score of 3.48 and Standard Deviation of .91. The implication is that several challenges militating against teachers’ capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state.

Research question 3: What are the strategies for improving teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state?

Table 8: Descriptive statistics on the strategies for improving teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state

S/N	Statements	N	SA	A	D	SD	REMARK
Q1	Attending seminars	330	106(32.1)	139(42.1)	76(23)	9(2.7)	Agreed
Q2	Attending workshops	330	112(33.9)	117(35.5)	72(21.9)	29(8.8)	Agreed
Q3	Attending conferences	330	107(32.4)	117(35.5)	64(19.4)	42(12.7)	Agreed
Q4	Use of mentorship	330	132(40.0)	155(47.0)	34(10.3)	9(2.7)	Agreed
Q5	Use of coaching	330	140(42.4)	155(47.0)	26(7.9)	9(2.7)	Agreed
Q6	Study leave with pay	330	189(57.3)	121(36.7)	18(5.5)	2(.6)	Agreed
Q7	Excursions,	330	80(24.2)	171(51.8)	65(19.7)	14(4.2)	Agreed
Q8	Symposiums	330	117(35.5)	159(48.2)	43(13.0)	11(3.3)	Agreed
Q9	Study leave with pay	330	120(36.4)	164(49.7)	35(10.6)	11(3.3)	Agreed
Q10	In-service training	330	151(45.9)	146(44.2)	26(7.9)	7(2.1)	Agreed
	TOTAL	3300	1254(38)	1444(43.8)	459(13.9)	143(4.3)	Agreed

Figures in parenthesis represent percentages (%)

Descriptive statistics on the strategies for improving teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state as depicted in Table 8 above revealed the respondents pools to be 1254(38), 1444(43.8), 459(13.9) and 143(4.3) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. The implication is that teacher' agreed that the itemized strategies are laudable for improving teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state.

Discussion of findings

The finding of the study reveals that that the extent to which teachers' capacity building can enhance the achievement of human capital development in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state was very high. This outcome agrees with Darling-Hammond (2012) who noted that realization of student achievement gains requires teachers to have; strong content knowledge; pedagogical knowledge and skills of how to teach others; understanding learners and their development; having general abilities for organizing, observing, explaining ideas, thinking diagnostically and having adaptive expertise for making judgment in light of student needs in a given context. Lamanauskas and Vilkoniene (2006) opined that acquiring appropriate

competencies in high schools science teachers is a guarantee for successful lesson delivery. Obanya (2010) posited that teachers remain essential actors and catalyst for change in all efforts aimed at promoting quality education in schools. In order to develop a responsive and effective teacher capable of undertaking the foregoing, Obanya (2010) argues that teachers require opportunities for continuous self-improvement; both career-long and career-wide opportunities that will enable them to acquire skills, knowledge and techniques needed for quality on the job performance.

The finding showed that there are several challenges militating against teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state. This conclusion agrees with Yara and Otieno (2010) who explained that the causes of poor students' performance, especially in mathematics are due to poor planning by teachers, inadequate teaching and learning resources and teacher shortages. In addition, poor students' performance has been blamed on teacher preparation

The finding showed that teachers agreed that the itemized strategies are laudable for improving teachers' capacity building in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state. This outcome correlates with the assertion of Amede (2018) who echoed that it is imperative for educational stakeholders to build teacher capacity through defined strategies by organizing seminars, workshops and conferences and to organize mentorship and coaching programs for teachers for overall development of their capacity. According to IR Global Rankings News Bulletin (2013), seminars and workshops allows participants to explore new ways of doing things, create value, adopt best practices, trends, technology and build networks. This is considered handy in efforts aimed at improving teaching skills and students' performance. However, contrary to the finding, teachers' capacity building through workshops are considered to be of short term nature, low intensity and unfocused activity (Cole, 2012).

Counselling Implications

Counsellors should use their lofty positions in the school system to encourage and motivate teachers to undergo professional development. They should regularly ensure the induction of new teachers through orientation and organize seminars, conference and workshops for old ones. These programmes when effectively and judiciously implemented would help to build teachers capacity.

Conclusion

The study examined teachers' capacity building as genuine mechanism for achieving human capital development in Nigeria. The outcome of the study revealed that the extent to which teachers' capacity building can enhance the achievement of in human capital development in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state is high. There are several challenges militating against teachers' capacity building training in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta state and that the itemized strategies are laudable for improving teachers' capacity building. However, effort should be made by government to provide enabling environment for teachers' to enable them participate fully in in-service training programme to enhance their intellectual and moral capacity.

Recommendations

1. Attention should be paid to capacity building development programmes that would make teaching career appealing and geared towards achieving human capital development in Nigeria.
2. Government should device more strategies that will enhance capacity building of teachers.
3. Educational administrators and policy formulators should implement policies that would surmount the challenges facing teachers' capacity building in Nigeria.

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